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**LOW-NICKEL STAINLESS STEEL PASSIVE FILM IN SIMULATED
CONCRETE PORE SOLUTION: A SIMS STUDY**

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Abstract

Low-nickel and AISI 304 austenitic stainless steel (SS) passive films were studied using secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS). An alkaline Ca(OH)₂ saturated test solution containing different chloride additions was used at room temperature. The passive film formed consists mainly of an inner chromium-rich oxide layer and an outer iron-rich oxide layer. The chemistry of the passive film depends strongly on the chloride content in the alkaline solution. Under these exposure conditions nickel was detected in the outer part of the oxide, whereas chloride ions were *not* found in the passive film for either the low-nickel or AISI 304 SS alloys.

Keywords: SIMS; Passive film; Low-nickel stainless steel; Concrete pore solution; Depth profile

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1. Introduction

Steel rebar embedded in concrete is protected from corrosion by a thin oxide layer that is formed and maintained on their surfaces because of the highly alkaline environment of the surrounding concrete, with a pH usually in the range 12-13 [1]. However, with time, severe corrosion may occur in reinforced concrete structures (RCS). Corrosion is most frequently induced by the entry of chloride ions, leading to localised corrosion activity. Chloride ions are commonly found in construction materials and may originate from contamination of the water used in concrete production, from contaminated aggregates, or even from the external environment, as in the case of marine environments or de-icing salts [2].

Austenitic stainless steels (SS) are alloys of great interest in technological applications where materials with high corrosion resistance are required. The stability of the surface oxide (i.e. passive film) formed on an austenitic SS depends mainly on the alloy composition, temperature, passivation time and working environment. These passive oxide films are of the order of only 1-4 nm thick and their analysis is therefore challenging [3].

The solid state properties of passive films formed on SS have been widely studied using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) and X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) techniques [4-8]. Secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) is well-suited for the study of surface oxidation phenomena related to sample transfer because it allows the detection of isotopes at very low concentration levels [9,10]. Previous studies have revealed that passive films formed on austenitic SS exposed to aqueous solutions are a mixture of iron and chromium oxides, with hydroxide and water-containing compounds concentrated in the outermost region of the film and chromium oxide enrichment at the metal/film interface [11].

In the literature it has been proposed that during the anodic dissolution of SS materials the alloying elements chromium, molybdenum and nickel are enriched at the metal/oxide interface in their metallic states and that nickel decreases the current in the passive state, hence enhancing the passivation of the alloy [12,13].

The SS offers exceptional advantages for certain applications in construction, combining intrinsic durability with aesthetics, strength, ductility and formability. However, their use as rebar has been limited due to the prohibitively high cost of SS compared to carbon steel. For this reason, new SSs, in which the nickel content has been lowered by replacement with other elements [14,15] (nickel is subject to considerable price fluctuations due to stock market factors), are being evaluated as possible alternatives to conventional carbon steel [16-18].

Low-nickel austenitic SSs exhibit attractive properties comparable to those of traditional austenitic SSs, such as good corrosion resistance, high levels of strength and ductility and reduced tendency of grain sensitization [19]. These low-nickel SSs should be highly nitrogen alloyed and have a well-balanced two-phase structure: 40% ferrite (α)-60% austenite (γ) up to 60% α -40% γ . The production of these low-nickel steels is made possible by the addition of manganese that increases the nitrogen solubility in the melt and significantly retards the tendency of nitride precipitation (such as chromium nitride, Cr_2N).

It has been reported that the oxide film breakdown occurs non-uniformly over the surface, starting from a number of activated sites which reaction products formed consist of voluminous non-protective hydroxide [20]. Several authors have reported on the effect of manganese on corrosion resistance, for instance, manganese decreases the pitting resistance of 18% chromium, 5% nickel, 10% manganese and 0.07-0.35% nitrogen alloy [21,22]. The

decrease of nickel, essentially a γ -stabiliser increasing pitting corrosion resistance [23], is compensated with an increase in nitrogen content. Manganese is an important γ -stabiliser and it also contributes to improved nitrogen solubility [14]. It is well-known that manganese and nickel promote austenitic microstructures which are more corrosion resistant in chloride media than the ferritic microstructure [23].

The different models proposed to describe the events leading to breakdown of the passive film can be classified into two groups attributing specific role to the chloride ion: adsorption of the chloride ions on the passive film, and ion migration or penetration of the chloride ions through the passive film to the metal surface [24-26].

The aim of this paper was to investigate the influence of chloride content in a simulated concrete pore solution on a low-nickel SS generated passive film using the SIMS technique. A conventional AISI 304 SS was also studied for comparative purposes. Special attention was paid to study the presence of chloride ion within the passive film.

2. Experimental

Low-nickel and AISI 304 austenitic SSs (from ACERINOX SA company, Palmones, Cádiz, Spain) plates of 0.5×0.5 cm were used. Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the two materials, provided by the manufacturer. Specimens were polished using a series of silicon carbide (SiC) emery papers down to grade 1200, and afterwards, using diamond paste of 1 μm , and then ultrasonically cleaned with ethanol and rinsed with water.

Table 1. Chemical composition (% by weight^a) of the tested low-nickel austenitic SS and AISI 304 austenitic SS.

The simulated concrete pore (SCP) solution was a calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) saturated solution with a pH ~12-13, with different amounts of sodium chloride (NaCl): 0, 0.4, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0 and 5.0% by weight. Specimens were immediately immersed in the solutions after the surface preparation. The total immersion time was 20 days. After that period of time, specimens were cleaned with isopropanol, ethanol and water and dried in N_2 in order to remove any surface contamination before analysis.

An Atomika 6500 was used for SIMS measurements. A primary ion beam of N_2^+ was used, with a beam energy of 500 eV and in normal incidence. The beam current was 50 nA. All craters were ~500 μm in diameter.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows chromium depth profile for AISI 304 SS (Fig. 1a) and for low-nickel SS (Fig. 1b) specimens after 20 days immersion in the SCP solution with different NaCl contents. Analysis was performed for 1200 seconds; however no changes were observed after 600 seconds, suggesting that the bulk alloy was reached within that period of time. For AISI 304 SS specimens in 0.0, 0.4, 1.0 and 2.0% NaCl, a peak is defined at similar depth sputtering time. However, for 3.0 and 5.0% NaCl, the chromium peaks were shifted towards the innermost region of the oxide layer, see Fig. 1a. These results may be interpreted as for chloride concentration $\leq 2.0\%$, a similar chromium enrichment is achieved on the oxide film. Nevertheless, for higher contents of chloride ions the chromium enrichment was lower and the Cr^+ peaks approached to the oxide/metal interface. Attempts were not made to absolutely quantify the oxide concentrations; measured SIMS intensities are heavily dependent on matrix effects and are not necessarily proportional to the

concentration of the element analysed so that, a quantification of the metal oxide profiles is virtually impossible [10]. It is assumed that the sputter rate is the same for all the passive oxides studied, so that a direct comparison between samples is thus valid [3].

Fig. 1b shows chromium depth profile for low-nickel SS specimens after 20 days immersion in the SCP solution with different NaCl contents. In this case, a coinciding peak can be observed for the specimens on which the passive layer was formed in SCP solution with 0.0, 0.4 and 1.0% NaCl content. For high NaCl content, a small shifting in the peaks position towards the oxide/metal interface is showed. Consequently, an influence in the chromium enrichment of the passive layer is also found for this material, but at a lower level of Cl addition to the SCP solution.

Fig. 1. Depth profiles for (a) AISI 304 SS, and (b) low-nickel SS specimens immersed in a simulated concrete pore solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing chromium content of the oxide layer. N_2^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 50 nA. Crater size of 500 μm .

Fig. 2 shows iron depth profile for AISI 304 SS (Fig. 2a) and for low-nickel SS (Fig. 2b) specimens after 20 days immersion in the SCP solution with different NaCl contents. Analysis was performed for 1200 seconds; however no changes were observed after 600 seconds, suggesting that the bulk alloy was reached within that period of time. As for chromium depth profiles using AISI 304 SS specimen (Fig. 1a), the passive layer formed in the SCP solution with concentration of NaCl between 0.0 and 2.0% showed a coinciding maxima in the depth profile when iron was monitored. For those specimens of AISI 304 SS where the passive layer was formed in the SCP solution with 3.0 and 5.0% NaCl content, the iron peaks were shifted towards the innermost region of the oxide layer,

see Fig. 2a. In addition, Fig. 2b shows iron depth profiles for low-nickel SS specimens, where a coinciding peak can be seen for those which formed their passive layer in the SPC solution with 0.0, 0.4 and 1.0% NaCl content. Peaks shifted towards the oxide/metal interface as NaCl concentration increased, see Fig. 2b.

Fig. 2. Depth profiles for (a) AISI 304 SS, and (b) low-nickel SS specimens immersed in simulated concrete pore solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing iron content of the oxide layer. N_2^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 50 nA. Crater size of 500 μm .

Comparing chromium (Fig. 1) and iron (Fig. 2) content in both AISI 304 and low-nickel SSs, it can be observed that there is a NaCl concentration threshold for each material above which the enrichment of chromium and iron decreases. The AISI 304 SS shows a chloride concentration threshold of 2.0%. Above this concentration, chromium and iron enrichment in the oxide decreases with regards to richness observed below this threshold. On the other hand, low-nickel SS shows a threshold in chloride concentration of 1.0%, for higher NaCl content the passive layer become poor in chromium and iron.

If the oxide layer of both AISI 304 and low-nickel SS materials are compared, it can be seen that although low-nickel SS exhibits a chloride threshold lower than AISI 304 SS and that the peaks below that threshold are slightly shifted towards oxide/metal interface, at the highest concentrations of NaCl (3.0 and 5.0%) the AISI 304 SS specimens show a lower enrichment in chromium and iron, which may indicate that passivity is directly related with the oxides content. This result should be related with a worse corrosion behaviour of AISI 304 SS.

An interesting point to note is that the iron peaks are all slightly shifted towards the outer surface of the film in comparison to the chromium peaks, indicating that there is a distinct separation between the iron and chromium oxides on the surface, corroborating the duplex layer nature of the passive film on stainless steel [20,27].

Fig. 3 shows nickel depth profile for AISI 304 SS (Fig. 3a) and for low-nickel SS (Fig. 3b) specimens after 20 days immersion in the SPC solution with different NaCl contents. Analysis was performed for 1200 seconds; however no changes were observed after 600 seconds, suggesting that the bulk alloy was reached within that period of time. In the absence of chloride in the SCP solution nickel was undetected in both materials. For the SCP solution polluted with NaCl, both AISI 304 and low-nickel SS materials show the presence of nickel in the oxide layer. A peak in the range of the peak detected for iron is found for both materials. The position of the peak indicates that nickel is present in the outermost region of the passive film. This finding is in agreement with reported results for austenitic SSs and is associated with the presence of traces of nickel [27,28]. A recent X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) study of the passive layer formed on SS in an alkaline 0.1M NaOH solution [29], found that the nickel contribution to the external region of the oxide film is a nickel-iron spinel, probably NiFe_2O_4 . In addition, a peak can be found in the range of the peak detected for chromium in AISI 304 (Fig. 3a), close to the oxide/metal interface. The depletion of the other elements in the alloy promotes nickel enrichment in this region. This tendency has also been reported by other authors for SS in alkaline and neutral solutions [30,31]. The amount of nickel in the passive films increases progressively with time and seems to be proportional to the bulk content [31], which explains that the oxide film in AISI 304 SS is nickel enriched in comparison to the one formed on the low-nickel SS.

Fig. 3. Depth profiles for (a) AISI 304 SS, and (b) low-nickel SS specimens immersed in simulated concrete pore solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing nickel content of the oxide layer. N_2^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 50 nA. Crater size of 500 μm .

Finally, the presence of chloride ions as part of the passive layer was analysed. Fig. 4 shows chloride depth profile for AISI 304 SS (Fig. 4a) and for low-nickel SS (Fig. 4b) specimens after 20 days immersion in the SCP solution with different NaCl contents. A peak located at the outermost region of the oxide film can be observed on AISI 304 SS specimen immersed in the SCP solution without chloride ions (Fig. 4a). Due to the lack of chloride ions, that peak may be attributed only to chloride ions from adsorption processes on the SS during surface preparation. When NaCl was added to the SCP solution, a coinciding peak can be observed, see Fig. 4a. That peak matches up with peak defined in the absence of chloride, which may be interpreted as the chloride is not part of the passive film, but the result of an adsorption process on the alloy surface. Low-nickel SS behaves in a similar way to AISI 304 SS, see Fig. 4b. Therefore, it may be stated that chloride ions do not participate in the passive layer structure of AISI 304 and low-nickel SSs under the experimental conditions tested.

Fig. 4. Depth profiles for (a) AISI 304 SS, and (b) low-nickel SS specimens immersed in simulated concrete pore solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing chloride content of the oxide layer. N_2^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 50 nA. Crater size of 500 μm .

4. Conclusions

The analysis of the SIMS spectra indicates a duplex layer structure of the passive film, whose inner layer is chromium oxide covered by an outer layer of iron oxide. Each material shows a different NaCl concentration threshold above which the relative amount of chromium and iron decreases, being the one corresponding to AISI 304 higher than the one corresponding to the low-nickel. Nickel is found in the outer part of the film. Finally, the chloride ions do not participate in the passive film structure of the low-nickel and AISI 304 SS alloys.

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Table 1. Chemical composition (% by weight^a) of the tested low-nickel austenitic SS and AISI 304 austenitic SS.

Material	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Mo	Cu	N
Low-Nickel	0.082	0.48	7.26	0.027	0.001	16.56	4.32	0.07	0.13	0.075
AISI 304	0.049	0.32	1.75	0.028	0.001	18.20	8.13	0.22	0.21	0.050

^a The balance was Fe.

CAPTIONS FOR ILLUSTRATIONS

Fig. 1. Depth profiles for (a) AISI 304 SS, and (b) low-nickel SS specimens immersed in a simulated concrete pore solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing chromium content of the oxide layer. N_2^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 50 nA. Crater size of 500 μm .

Fig. 2. Depth profiles for (a) AISI 304 SS, and (b) low-nickel SS specimens immersed in simulated concrete pore solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing iron content of the oxide layer. N_2^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 50 nA. Crater size of 500 μm .

Fig. 3. Depth profiles for (a) AISI 304 SS, and (b) low-nickel SS specimens immersed in simulated concrete pore solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing nickel content of the oxide layer. N_2^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 50 nA. Crater size of 500 μm .

Fig. 4. Depth profiles for (a) AISI 304 SS, and (b) low-nickel SS specimens immersed in simulated concrete pore solution with different concentrations of NaCl, showing chloride content of the oxide layer. N_2^+ primary beam, 500 eV, 50 nA. Crater size of 500 μm .

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4